

Response of Eight Flax Cultivars to Some Growth and Yield Traits Under Different Levels of Water Stress

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Abstract

A field experiment was conducted in Al-Hussainiya District, 20 km northeast of Karbala province, during the winter season (2023-2024) to study the effect of water stress on several flax cultivars. The experiment was implemented in a split-plot arrangement according to a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with three replicates. The main plots included three levels of water stress (line treatment, 50% depletion of available water, 70% depletion of available water, and 90% depletion of available water), while the sub-plots included eight flax genotypes (Indian, Polish, Syrian, Sakha 5, Sakha 6, Giza 8, Giza 10, and Giza 11). The results showed that the Sakha 5 cultivar was excelled in the number of leaves and leaf area, which reached (597.0 leaves.plant⁻¹, 897.6 cm²), respectively, while the Syrian cultivar was excelled in the early flowering, which reached (90.88 days), while the Giza 10 cultivar was excelled in the activity of the peroxidase enzyme, which reached (55.94 absorption units g⁻¹). The plants of the 11 cultivar were superior in the weight of 1000 seeds, seed yield, and oil percentage, which reached (11.39 g, 1228.2 kg ha⁻¹, 56.228%), while the plants in the irrigation treatment (50% depletion of ready water) were excelled in the number of leaves, leaf area, weight of 1000 seeds, seed yield, and oil percentage, as follows (613.3 leaves.plant⁻¹, 982.4 cm².plant⁻¹, 11.38 g). 1356.7 kg ha⁻¹, 58.18%), respectively, compared to plants in the irrigation treatment (70% depletion of available water) and the irrigation treatment (90% depletion of available water).

Keywords: *water stress, flax cultivation, irrigation treatment, yield.*

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Introduction

Flax (*Linum usitatissimum* L.), a member of the Linaceae family, is an important agricultural crop globally and in the Arab world. It is diploid (2n = 30), self-pollinating, and is cultivated for its seeds, which are rich in valuable oils and fibers. Flax is of great economic and nutritional importance. The production of flax oil and fiber is a cornerstone of many industries, while its seeds are a rich food source of unsaturated fatty acids, such as oleic acid (19-20%), linoleic acid (17-19%), and linolenic acid (45-60%), making them highly nutritious and offering health benefits such as helping to treat cardiovascular diseases (El-Gedwy, 2020). Flaxseed oil (the residue left over from the seed after oil extraction) is also used in animal feed and

in organic industries (Mahmoud, 2024). The Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) reported that the flax cultivation area in 2021 was approximately 241,103 hectares, with a production capacity of 896,636.43 tons (Nemer, 2023). A disparity in global production has also been noted, with Canada being the largest producer, followed by China, India, the United States, Ethiopia, and Egypt (FAO, 2019). In Iraq, flax cultivation areas remain limited, due to several reasons, including the focus on other strategic crops, lack of interest in this crop, and the absence of necessary processing industries. Plants in general, and flax in particular, face water availability problems due to water scarcity and climate change, which is one of the most serious environmental challenges facing humanity. This causes a shortage of arable water and more extreme weather pressures. It has become necessary to utilize modern scientific methods to bridge the irrigation water deficit and regulate or schedule crop irrigation to achieve an optimal state and create a balance between water consumption and crop yield (Al-Khafaji, 2023). When plants experience stress, a series of physical and chemical signals are triggered at the molecular and cellular levels to protect the plant from stress (Jiang et al., 2013; Li, et al., 2019). Most plants have developed specialized mechanisms at the physiological and molecular levels to survive and withstand stress (Shi et al., 2018; Li, et al., 2019). Stress often leads to the formation of ROS, which degrade unsaturated fats. High concentrations of ROS can lead to toxic stress in cells, resulting in cellular dysfunction and tissue damage (Li, et al., 2019). Drought stress significantly affects flax seedling growth, flowering, seed development, and yield (Dash, et al., 2023). The accumulation of ROS increases cellular oxidative stress, leading to the loss of economic yield, i.e., oil, fiber, and nutrients in flax (Dash, et al., 2023).

Flax genetics vary greatly in their tolerance to water stress (Mostafavi, 2011; Dash, et al., 2023). Flax cultivars grown under drought conditions exhibited a wide range of variations in traits such as grain yield, plant height, and thousand-seed weight (Diederichsen, et al. 2006; Dash, et al., 2023).

Materials and Methods

Experimental location and Soil Properties

A field experiment was conducted in the fields of Al-Hussainiya District, Karbala Province to determine the performance of eight flax cultivars under the influence of water stress during the winter season of 2023-2024. In a silty clay loam soil, the relationship between structural stress and moisture content was estimated for a field soil sample sifted with a 2 mm sieve to estimate the soil's water-holding capacity (Khaleel, & Al-Furaiji, 2023). Different stresses (33, 100, 300, 500, 1000, and 1500) kPa were applied to the soil (Al-Khafagi, & Al-Nuaimi, 2023). The available soil water content was calculated from the difference in the volumetric moisture content at the field capacity and the wilting point (Al-Khafagi, & Al-Nuaimi, 2023).

Land preparation and agricultural operations

The experimental land was plowed twice perpendicularly using a disc plow, then smoothed and leveled to create a suitable seedbed. The land was then divided according to the field plan for the experiment, which included 72 experimental units distributed across three replicates, with 24 experimental units per replicate. The experimental unit area was 4 m² (2 x 2 m).

Experimental Design and Experimental Treatments

A factorial experiment according to the RCBD design, with a split-plot arrangement, with three replications, included three irrigation water addition treatments placed in the main plots: irrigation at 50% depletion (control treatment), 70%, and 90% of the available water intake. The secondary plots included eight flax cultivars (Indian, Polish, Syrian, Sakha 5, Sakha 6, Giza 8, Giza 10, and Giza 11).

Irrigation Method and Monitoring of Treatment Moisture Depletion

Irrigation was carried out using a gasoline-powered pump with a discharge pipe fitted with a meter to measure the amount of water. The pump was connected to a network of plastic pipes distributed throughout the experimental units. Equal amounts of water were added to all plots at planting time.

The following traits were studied for a random sample of ten plants (recorded as an average, randomly selected from the two medians of each experimental unit) as follows:

Number of leaves (leaf per plant) calculated as the average of the leaves of ten plants.

Total leaf area per plant (cm².plant⁻¹): The area of each treatment was calculated for each replicate using ImageJ on the Windows 7 operating system. The total leaf area was calculated by multiplying the leaf area by the number of leaves per plant (Carvalho et al., 2017).

Time to 50% flowering (days): The number of days taken from the date of the first irrigation until 50% of the plants flowered was recorded for each experimental unit. 4-Peroxidase activity (absorption unit g⁻¹).

POD activity was determined according to the method described by (Nezih, 1985).

Weight of 1000 seeds (g): 1000seeds were weighed in grams using a sensitive balance after seeds were randomly taken from each plant.

Seed yield (kg h⁻¹): The seed weight of the plants in the experimental unit (4 m²) was calculated and then converted to kg h⁻¹ according to the following equation:

$$\text{Seed yield (kg h}^{-1}\text{)} = \text{Experimental unit yield (kg)} \times 10 \quad (1)$$

Experimental unit area (m²)

Oil percentage (%)

Fat was estimated based on the AOAC 1995 method, using a Soxhlet apparatus, according to the following equation (Khaleel, & Al-Furaiji, 2023):

$$\text{Fat percentage (\%)} = \frac{\text{Weight of the flask before extraction} - \text{Weight of the flask after extraction}}{\text{Weight of the sample}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Results and Discussion

Number of Leaves (Leaf per Plant)

The statistical analysis data in Table 1 indicate a significant effect between flax cultivars and irrigation treatments, as well as an interaction between them, on the average number of leaves. The Sakha 5 cultivar outperformed the average number of leaves, reaching 597.0 leaves per plant, which did not differ significantly from the Polish cultivar, which had an average number of leaves of 597.0 leaves per plant. The lowest average leaf number was recorded in the Giza 8 cultivar, which achieved an average of 406.9 leaves per plant. It also did not significantly differ from the Sakha 6 cultivar, which achieved an average of 407.6 leaves per plant. The reason for the variation in average leaf number among cultivars is due to variations in their genetic makeup and response to environmental conditions. The results also showed a significant effect of irrigation treatments on the average number of leaves, as the irrigation treatment (90% depletion of available water) gave the lowest average number of leaves, reaching 330.7 leaves per

plant-1, while the control treatment achieved the highest average number of leaves, reaching 613.3 leaves per plant-1, which also differed significantly from the irrigation treatment (70% depletion of available water), as it gave an average number of leaves of 500.8 leaves . plant-1. The interaction effect between the two study factors was significant on the average number of leaves, as the Polonian cultivar in the irrigation treatment (50% depletion of available water) gave the highest interaction value, reaching 741.7 leaves per plant-1, which did not differ significantly from the Sakha 5 cultivar, which gave an interaction value of 733.0 leaves per plant-1 compared to the Giza 8 cultivar in the irrigation treatment (90% depletion of available water), which gave the lowest interaction value, reaching 246.2 leaves per plant-1. Water stress activates a group of hydrolytic enzymes, as well as proteins. These enzymes break down large molecules such as proteins, starch, and nucleic acids into their building blocks. These enzymes include nucleases and rib nucleases, which break down DNA and RNA. The activity of these enzymes increases most during severe stress. It is well known that severe stress accelerates tissue death, especially in leaves, leading to their death and shedding. Death is preceded by the decomposition of cell components and their transfer to new tissues before the leaf detaches from the plant. (Abu Jadallah, 2018).

Table 1. Effect of Irrigation Levels, Cultivars, and Their Interactions on the Average Number of Leaves (Leaf per Plant) in Flax Plants

cultivars	treatments irrigation			average cultivars
	50%	70%	90%	
Indian	558.5	488.3	318.7	455.1
Polish	741.7	604.1	438.3	594.7
Syrian	612.7	488.5	340.0	480.4
Giza 10	565.1	457.7	266.5	429.8
Sakha 5	733.0	626.0	432.0	597.0
Sakha 6	531.6	435.0	256.1	407.6
Giza 11	621.2	475.2	348.1	481.5
Giza 8	542.6	432.0	246.2	406.9
Average treatments	613.3	500.8	330.7	
L.S.D 0.05				
cultivars		irrigation		interaction
25.14		20.26		43.21

Leaf Area (cm²/plant-1)

The results of the statistical analysis in Table 2 showed a highly significant effect of both irrigation treatments and cultivars, as well as their interaction, on the leaf area trait. This indicates substantial differences between treatments when analyzing leaf area averages. When examining the effect of cultivars, we note that cultivars had a significant effect on the average leaf area. The Giza 5 cultivar recorded the highest average leaf area, reaching 897.6 cm²/plant-1, followed by the Polonian cultivar with an average area of 852.6 cm²/plant-1. Meanwhile, the Sakha 6 cultivar had the lowest average area of 548.4 cm²/plant-1. This indicates that there are genetic differences between cultivars in their ability to produce leaf area. The results also indicate a significant effect of irrigation levels and average leaf area. The irrigation treatment (90% depletion of available water) produced the lowest average leaf area, reaching 409.9 cm².plant-1, while the area increased significantly in the irrigation treatment (70% depletion of available water), reaching 687.2 cm².plant-1. The control treatment (50% depletion of available water) achieved the highest average area, reaching 982.4 cm².plant-1. This indicates that reducing the amount of available water negatively affects the growth of flax leaf area. The cultivars showed significant variation in leaf area, which may be explained by the fact that the Sakha 5 cultivar may possess genetic traits that

make it more capable of utilizing water resources efficiently and tolerating different environmental conditions. Conversely, the Sakha 6 cultivar recorded the lowest leaf area, indicating that this cultivar is weak in leaf area formation or sensitive to water shortages or certain environmental conditions. Regarding the interaction between irrigation and cultivars, the Sakha 5 cultivar recorded the highest leaf area at 1269.7 cm²/plant, indicating that this cultivar responds positively to good irrigation. In contrast, the Giza 8 cultivar recorded the lowest leaf area at 319.0 cm²/plant, reflecting the impact of water stress on this cultivar in particular.

Table 2. Effect of Irrigation Levels, Cultivars, and Their Interaction on the Average Leaf Area (cm²/plant) of Flax

cultivars	treatments irrigation			average cultivars
	50%	70%	90%	
Indian	1171.2	667.4	371.9	736.9
Polish	1242.4	808.9	506.5	852.6
Syrian	911.8	662.8	396.7	657.1
Giza 10	768.5	617.5	333.9	573.3
Sakha 5	1269.7	866.3	556.8	897.6
Sakha 6	714.9	600.2	330.9	548.7
Giza 11	1015.1	698.6	463.3	725.7
Giza 8	765.7	575.4	319.0	553.4
Average treatments	982.4	687.2	409.9	
L.S.D 0.05				
cultivars		irrigation		interaction
33.78		24.81		57.48

Number of Days from Planting to 50% Flowering

Cultivars showed a significant effect on the number of days from planting to 50% flowering. The results in Table 3 show that the cultivars differed among themselves in the duration to flowering. The Syrian cultivar produced the earliest average for the trait, at 90.88 days, followed by the Polish cultivar and the Giza 8 cultivar, with average durations of 92.73 and 92.75 days, respectively. Meanwhile, the Sakha 5 genotype achieved the longest duration, at 103.31 days. This may be due to the variation in genotypes in early maturity due to genetic factors that control the factors affecting the trait, such as the number of days from planting and the rate of growth resulting from cell division (Elayan et al., 2015). This result is consistent with what Jassim (2021) found. The same table indicates significant differences between water stress treatments. The irrigation treatment (90% depletion of available water) recorded the lowest average number of days from planting to 50% flowering, at 82.93 days. The highest average for this trait was recorded in the control treatment (50% depletion of available water), at 109.82 days. It also differed significantly from the irrigation treatment (70% depletion of available water), which reached 94.68 days. The reason for the shortened period from planting to flowering is due to the limited water supply, high temperatures and winds, and low relative humidity levels. This increased the speed of physiological processes as a response and alert to escape drought and reach the flowering stage, enabling the plant to complete its life cycle and produce seeds to preserve the species. (Abu Jadallah (2018) The two-way interaction between cultivars and irrigation treatments had a significant effect on the same trait. The Polish cultivar, under the irrigation treatment (90% depletion of available water), had the lowest mean for the trait, at 78.68 days, which was not significantly different from the Syrian cultivar under the same irrigation treatment. Meanwhile, the Sakha 5 cultivar, under the control treatment, had an average number of days from planting to 50% flowering of 117.56 days.

Table 3. Effect of Irrigation Levels and Cultivars on the Number of Days from Planting to 50% Flowering in Flax Plants

cultivars	treatments irrigation			average cultivars
	50%	70%	90%	
Indian	112.21	95.74	84.06	97.34
Polish	107.73	91.79	78.68	92.73
Syrian	103.92	89.18	79.56	90.88
Giza 10	109.85	93.74	84.34	95.98
Sakha 5	117.56	103.40	88.96	103.31
Sakha 6	112.23	95.98	81.90	96.70
Giza 11	109.02	96.63	84.76	96.80
Giza 8	106.06	91.003	81.20	92.75
Average treatments irrigation	109.82	94.68	82.93	
L.S.D 0.05				
cultivars		irrigation		interaction
0.538		0.600		0.977

Peroxidase (POD) Enzyme Activity (absorption unit g-1)

The results in Table 4 showed significant differences between flax cultivars in peroxidase enzyme activity. The Giza 10 cultivar recorded the highest average enzyme activity, reaching 55.94 PDU g-1. There were no significant differences between it and the Giza 11 cultivar, which recorded an enzyme activity of 53.16 PDU g-1. The Indian cultivar produced the lowest average for this trait, reaching 29.59 PDU g-1. This is due to the differences in the genetic characteristics of the flax cultivars. The results in the same table show a significant increase in the effectiveness of enzyme antioxidants with increasing water stress, as the irrigation treatment (90% depletion of ready water) achieved the highest average peroxidase enzyme activity of 59.94 absorption units g-1, which differed significantly from the two irrigation treatments (50% depletion and 70% depletion of ready water), as they recorded an average enzyme activity of 36.96 and 43.56, respectively. The increased activity of peroxidase is due to the increase in amino acids or soluble proteins in the cell cytoplasm, which may contribute to increased enzyme synthesis and effectiveness. This enzyme works to detoxify free radicals by acting as a complementary group, accelerating the oxidation of protons, producing compounds that bind to H₂O₂ and subsequently break down H₂O₂, thus eliminating its toxicity. It also stimulates and accelerates the conversion of H₂O₂ into water and oxygen, in addition to its role in increasing the stability of the cell membrane and chlorophyll (Valero, & Egusquiza, 2023). Therefore, the activity of peroxidase increases in response to curbing the harmful effects of water stress (Das and Roychoudhury, 2014; Valero, & Egusquiza, 2023). The two-way interaction between cultivars and irrigation treatments had a significant effect on the same trait. The Giza 11 cultivar had the highest average peroxidase activity, reaching 73.33 absorptive units g-1 in the irrigation treatment (90% water consumption), compared to the Indian cultivar, which recorded the lowest average for the trait in the control treatment (50% water consumption), reaching 27.21 absorptive units g-1.

Table 4. Effect of Cultivars, Irrigation Levels, and Their Interaction on Peroxidase Activity (absorption units g-1) in Flax Plants

cultivars	treatments irrigation			average cultivars
	50%	70%	90%	
Indian	27.21	28.53	33.03	29.59
Polish	33.01	33.63	59.73	42.13
Syrian	33.17	42.17	69.07	48.13
Giza 10	47.30	55.90	64.63	55.94

Sakha 5	39.13	47.40	67.83	51.46
Sakha 6	38.17	48.42	55.83	47.47
Giza 11	39.37	46.78	73.33	53.16
Giza 8	38.37	45.63	56.03	46.68
Average treatments	irrigation	36.96	43.56	59.94
L.S.D 0.05				
cultivars	irrigation	interaction		
4.001	2.662	6.748		

Weight of 1000 Seeds (g)

The results in Table 5 show a significant difference between flax cultivars in 1000 seed weight during the experimental season. The Giza 11 cultivar plants had the highest content of this trait, reaching 11.39 g, compared to the Sakha 5 cultivar, which recorded the lowest average 1000 seed weight, reaching 7.16 g. Seed weight is a component of yield and is related to the efficiency of carbon assimilation and the efficiency of the source-to-sink relationship. Seed weight is determined by plant activity, the number of seeds formed in the plant, and the amount of available metabolites (Andrade, 2000). The reason for the increased 1000-seed weight in the Giza 11 cultivar is attributed to the small number of capsules per plant and the small number of seeds per capsule, which resulted in the seed receiving a greater amount of metabolites, thus increasing its weight. This difference between flax cultivars was found by Abd El-Mohsen et al. (2013), Shakya and Barwa (2017), Al-Samarrai (2019), Al-Hiti (2021), Jassim (2021), and Al-Taie (2022), who indicated a significant difference in 1000-seed weight between flax cultivars. Irrigation treatments significantly affected the average weight of 1000 seeds. The irrigation treatment (90% depletion of available water) gave the lowest average weight of 1000 seeds, reaching 6.96 g, compared to the two irrigation treatments (50% depletion and 70% depletion of available water), which gave average weights of 1000 seeds of 11.38 g and 9.58 g, respectively. The reason for the low grain weight is attributed to the lack of water supply during the flowering stage and the decreased efficiency of photosynthesis and material transfer during the filling stage (Ramya et al., 2022). The interaction effect between the two study factors was significant on the average weight of 1,000 seeds. The Giza 11 cultivar achieved the highest interaction value, reaching 13.50 g, in the control treatment (50% depletion of available water), while the Sakha 5 cultivar achieved the lowest interaction value, reaching 4.92 g, in the irrigation treatment (90% depletion of available water).

Table 5. Effect of Irrigation Levels, Cultivars, and Their Interaction on the Weight of 1,000 Seeds (g)

cultivars	treatments irrigation			average cultivars
	50%	70%	90%	
Indian	11.153	9.577	7.157	9.296
Polish	9.580	7.283	5.000	7.288
Syrian	11.327	9.853	7.723	9.634
Giza 10	12.620	10.617	8.207	10.481
Sakha 5	9.250	7.320	4.927	7.166
Sakha 6	10.520	8.530	6.097	8.382
Giza 11	13.503	11.970	8.700	11.391
Giza 8	13.133	11.520	7.917	10.857
Average treatments	irrigation	11.386	9.584	6.966
L.S.D 0.05				
cultivars	irrigation	interaction		
0.175	0.130	0.298		

Total Seed Yield (kg ha-1)

The results of Table 6 show a significant difference between flax cultivars in total seed yield for the two experimental seasons. The Giza 11 cultivar had the highest total seed yield, reaching 1228.2 kg ha-1 for the experimental season, compared to the Sakha 5 cultivar, which recorded the lowest average seed yield, reaching 846.0 kg ha-1. The reason for the increase in total seed yield in the Giza 11 cultivar is attributed to the cultivar's genetic and epigenetic differences, in addition to its excelled in most growth traits, which led to the highest increase in seed yield compared to other cultivars. This result is consistent with the results obtained by El-Borhamy (2016), Al-Sudani (2018), Al-Samarrai (2019), Al-Hiti (2021), Jassim (2021), and Al-Taie (2022). Irrigation treatments significantly affected the average total seed yield. The irrigation treatment (90% depletion of available water) produced the lowest average seed yield, reaching 777.1 kg ha-1, while the control treatment (50% depletion of available water) achieved the highest average yield, reaching 1356.7 kg ha-1. This also differed significantly from the irrigation treatment (70% depletion of available water), which achieved an average seed yield of 1048.7 kg ha-1. The reason for the lower total grain yield in the irrigation treatment (90% depletion of available water) is attributed to reduced growth characteristics and yield components. The interaction effect between the two study factors was significant on the average total seed yield. The Giza 11 cultivar achieved the highest interaction value, reaching 1550.1 kg ha-1, in the control treatment (50% depletion of available water), while the Sakha 5 cultivar achieved the lowest interaction value, reaching 600.4 kg ha-1, in the irrigation treatment (90% depletion of available water).

Table 6. Effect of Irrigation Levels, Cultivars, and Their Interaction on Total Seed Yield (kg ha-1).

cultivars	treatments irrigation			average cultivars
	50%	70%	90%	
Indian	1317.4	955.1	714.2	995.6
Polish	1124.6	835.7	632.9	864.4
Syrian	1428.6	1084.9	839.4	1117.6
Giza 10	1461.6	1155.9	834.7	1150.7
Sakha 5	1092.3	847.0	600.4	846.6
Sakha 6	1393.5	1112.1	824.1	1109.9
Giza 11	1550.1	1231.2	903.5	1228.2
Giza 8	1485.2	1167.4	868.0	1173.5
Average irrigation treatments	1356.7	1048.7	777.1	
L.S.D 0.05				
cultivars		irrigation		interaction
29.97		13.72		49.48

Seed Oil Content (%)

The statistical analysis results show significant differences between flax cultivars and irrigation treatments, as well as their interaction in the average seed oil content (see Table 7). The Giza 11 cultivar had the highest average oil content, reaching 56.228%, while the Sakha 5 cultivar had the lowest average seed oil content, reaching 52.392%. The difference in seed oil content between flax cultivars may be attributed to the genetic makeup of each cultivar and its response to environmental conditions. This is consistent with the research of Casa (1999) and Gallardo et al. (2014), who indicated that the oil content in flax seeds depends on the nature of the cultivar's genetic material. This also agrees with the findings of Al-Sudani (2018), Al-Samarrai (2019), Jassim (2021) and Al-Taie (2022). Irrigation treatments significantly affected the average seed oil percentage. The irrigation treatment (90% depletion of available water) produced the lowest average oil percentage, reaching 51.03%, compared to the two irrigation treatments (50%

depletion and 70% depletion of available water), which produced average oil percentages of 58.18% and 55.19%, respectively. The interaction effect between the two study factors was significant on the average seed oil percentage. The Giza 11 cultivar in the control treatment (50% depletion of available water) achieved the highest interaction value, reaching 59.77%, while the Sakha 5 cultivar in the irrigation treatment (90% depletion of available water) produced the lowest interaction value, reaching 48.37%.

Table 7. Effect of Irrigation Levels, Cultivars, and Their Interaction on Oil Percentage

cultivars	treatments irrigation			average cultivars
	50%	70%	90%	
Indian	58.367	55.257	51.097	54.907
Polish	58.200	55.087	50.953	54.747
Syrian	57.900	54.583	50.137	54.207
Giza 10	57.127	55.730	51.750	54.869
Sakha 5	56.293	52.510	48.373	52.392
Sakha 6	59.023	56.080	52.190	55.764
Giza 11	59.773	56.380	52.530	56.228
Giza 8	58.753	55.900	51.277	55.310
Average treatments irrigation	58.180	55.191	51.038	
L.S.D 0.05				
cultivars	irrigation		interaction	
0.090	0.099		0.163	

Conclusion

Eight flax cultivars' responses to varying degrees of water stress were shown to exhibit significant genotypic variation in this study. Especially under the ideal irrigation regime (50% available water depletion), the Giza 11 cultivar continuously outperformed other cultivars in important yield components such as 1000-seed weight, total seed yield, and oil percentage. On the other hand, the Syrian cultivar displayed early flowering, and Sakha 5 excelled in vegetative growth (leaf number and area). The results highlight how important it is to choose the right cultivar and manage water properly in order to maximize flax production. In conditions comparable to the study area, Giza 11 offers the most promising alternative for attaining high yield and oil content when water availability is moderate. The physiological processes behind Giza 11's superior performance could be investigated further, and these cultivars could be tested under a wider range of environmental conditions.

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